

Multiple Constrained MPCs for glucose regulation in Type 1 Diabetes ¹

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Abstract: This study introduces a personalized Model Predictive Control (MPC) strategy for managing type 1 diabetes, specifically addressing intra-day variability in glucose regulation. The proposed method uses a soft-switching mechanism combining multiple MPCs, each optimized for distinct day periods (breakfast, lunch, and dinner). Patient-specific models were identified using an enhanced impulse response technique, featuring a novel clinically-based cost function to better capture circadian dynamics. A switching mechanism ensures smooth transitions between controllers, minimizing disruptions. Performance was evaluated using the FDA-approved UVA/Padova simulator, demonstrating a 20% improvement in model fit and enhanced control performance compared to the state-of-art approach. The strategy consistently prevented hypoglycemia while improving time-in-target metrics.

Keywords: Artificial pancreas, Diabetes, Personalization, Constrained Model Predictive Control, Control of physiological systems

1. INTRODUCTION

Type 1 Diabetes (T1D) is a widespread autoimmune disease that affects millions of people worldwide in all age groups, as noted in Sun et al. (2022). The absence of insulin in patients with T1D results in prolonged periods of hyperglycemia (Blood Glucose (BG) > 180 [mg/dl]), which can have harmful long-term effects. External insulin injections allow patients with T1D to manage elevated BG levels. However, the dosage has to be carefully computed to avoid the dangerous condition of hypoglycemia (BG < 70 [mg/dl]). The progress in subcutaneous (sc) Continuous Glucose Monitors (CGMs) and sc insulin pumps has enabled the creation of an Artificial Pancreas (AP), a closed-loop system designed to automatically regulate BG levels (Cobelli et al. (2011)). This system integrates a CGM, an insulin pump, and a control algorithm that determines the optimal therapy. One of the most promising control techniques revealed to be the Model Predictive Control (MPC) algorithm that achieved successful results in the AP context, both in silico and in vivo (Toffanin et al. (2017); Dassau et al. (2013)). The MPC algorithm uses a dynamic model of T1D patients to predict near-

future BG levels and determine the optimal insulin dose accordingly. One of the key ingredients for the success of MPC is the accuracy of the predictive model. However, model identification in this context presents significant challenges due to two main factors: (i) identifiability issues arising from the simultaneous and opposing effects of insulin and meal intake on BG levels, making it difficult to distinguish their effect from the data; and (ii) inter- and intra-patient variability, which arises from differences in insulin sensitivity and glucose metabolism both across and within patients over time. In the state of the art, strategies addressing these challenges include: (i) the Impulse Response (IR) identification technique, which aids in distinguishing input effects on the BG levels; and (ii) the Daily Model Predictor (DMP) approach, which employs a patient-tailored daily model to address the inter-patient variability (Toffanin and Magni (2023b)). However, 20% of the 100 virtual patients in the UVA/Padova simulator (Visentin et al. (2018)) fail to achieve satisfactory performance with the DMP due to significant intra-day fluctuations in insulin sensitivity. To address this limitation, Toffanin et al. (2019) introduced the concept of employing multiple models, each tailored to a specific Day Period (DP), and integrating them to form the Multiple Model Predictor (MMP). Incorporating time-varying dynamics has demonstrated potential in more effectively capturing the intra-day variability. However, embedding the MMP within the MPC framework introduces further complexities: designing a MPC for systems with switching dynamics poses significant challenges, particularly in practical applications like AP systems characterized by

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strict safety constraints (Toffanin et al. (2019)). For this reason, a switching MPC control approach is proposed in this work, where three MPCs, each one designed on a linear time-invariant model, are integrated using weighted combinations of their suggestions to effectively handle the system's switching dynamics.

This work proposes two primary contributions: (i) an enhanced model identification approach with a clinically-based cost function to better model the circadian dynamics of the patient; and (ii) the design of a soft switching MPC control strategy, which involves multiple MPCs, each tailored to a different DP. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces an enhanced IR model identification technique with a clinically-based optimization function. Section 3 discusses the implementation of the switching MPC control algorithm. Section 4 presents the performance metrics, describes the UVA/Padova simulator, outlines the scenarios and presents the simulation results. Section 5 provides the conclusions.

2. MODEL IDENTIFICATION

Patient-tailored model identification is a non trivial process due to: (i) high inter-subject, and (ii) intra-subject variability, and (iii) the synchronization of meals and insulin that complicates the identification of their effects. Moreover the presence of other factors, like exercise and illness, further complicate it. A promising method for accurate model identification is the IR identification (Toffanin et al. (2019)), which has shown success with both simulated and real patient data. This method consists in identifying two Transfer Functions (TFs), $G_u(s)$ and $G_d(s)$, such that the Laplace transform of the CGM, $CGM(s)$, can be written as:

$$CGM(s) = G_u(s)U(s) + G_d(s)D(s)$$

with

$$G_u(s) = \frac{\mu_u e^{-\tau_u s}}{(1 + sT_{u1})(1 + sT_{u2})(1 + sT_{u3})(1 + sT_{u4})}$$

$$G_d(s) = \frac{\mu_d}{(1 + sT_{d1})(1 + sT_{d2})(1 + sT_{d3})}$$

where $U(s)$ and $D(s)$ are the Laplace transform of the differential insulin and meals with respect to their steady-state values, respectively, and the TFs' order and the insulin delay ($\tau_u = 15$ [min]) were selected with a trial and error procedure (Toffanin et al. (2019)). The IR identification technique is composed of two separate steps: the first one (step 1) uses exciting ad-hoc simulation data (IR data not collectable on real subjects for safety reasons) of the average patient of the UVA/Padova simulator. The model obtained from step 1 is then used as initialization for a personalization carried out in step 2. A constrained optimization problem is formulated to optimize the TFs parameters minimizing a new clinically-based cost function proposed in this work and defined as:

$$SSR_\eta = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N \left[\eta_j \left(\hat{Y}(j) - Y(j) \right) \right]^2}$$

where \hat{Y} and Y are the vectors representing the predicted and the real CGM, respectively, N denotes their length and the prediction error is weighted by a factor $\eta_j = 1 +$

Fig. 1. BGI as in (1) (blue solid line). Glucose target \tilde{y} represented by the orange dashed line.

$\frac{BGI(Y(j))}{100}$ which asymmetrically weights hypo, hyper and normoglycemia based on the Blood Glucose Index (BGI, Fig. 1), defined in Kovatchev et al. (2005) as:

$$BGI(Y(j)) = 10 \left[1.509 \left(\ln(Y(j))^{1.084} - \ln(\tilde{y})^{1.084} \right) \right]^2 \quad (1)$$

and \tilde{y} is the output target. The continuous-time system is then discretized via zero-order hold method obtaining $G_u(z)$ and $G_d(z)$ with sampling time T_s .

2.1 Delay Implementation

To model the input delay of the identified models, the states' augmentation method was applied: it maintains the model linear, and it is an easily scalable technique for delays having a low value of delay to sample time ratio. Consider the linear discrete-time system obtained via IR technique described as follows:

$$\tilde{x}(k+1) = \tilde{A}\tilde{x}(k) + \tilde{B}u(k-\tau) + \tilde{M}d(k)$$

$$y(k) = \tilde{C}\tilde{x}(k)$$

where $\tilde{x}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state vector ($n = 7$), $u(k) = i(k) - i_b(k) \in \mathbb{R}$ [pmol/Kg] is the difference between the injected insulin (i) and its basal value (i_b) that is time-varying. Note that the insulin level is normalized by the patient body weight. $d(k)$ [mg] represents the meal and $y(k) = \hat{Y}(k) - G_b \in \mathbb{R}$ [mg/dl] is the difference between the predicted CGM and the glucose basal value (G_b). $\tau = \text{round}(\tau_u/T_s)$, $\tau \in \mathbb{N}$ (here, $\text{round}(\cdot)$ represents the operation of rounding to the nearest integer), represents the delay to sample time ratio acting on the insulin. The augmented model incorporates the delay effect by augmenting the state vector, mapping delays to poles in $z = 0$, as follows:

$$\tilde{x}_j(t) = u(k-j) \implies \tilde{x}_j(k+1) = \tilde{x}_{j-1}(k), \quad j = 1, \dots, \tau$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{x}(k+1) \\ \tilde{x}_\tau(k+1) \\ \tilde{x}_{\tau-1}(k+1) \\ \vdots \\ \tilde{x}_1(k+1) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{A} & \tilde{B} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{x}(k) \\ \tilde{x}_\tau(k) \\ \tilde{x}_{\tau-1}(k) \\ \vdots \\ \tilde{x}_1(k) \end{bmatrix} +$$

$$+ [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 1]^\top u(k) + [\tilde{M} \ 0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]^\top d(k)$$

$$y(k) = [\tilde{C} \ 0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0] \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{x}(k) \\ \tilde{x}_\tau(k) \\ \tilde{x}_{\tau-1}(k) \\ \vdots \\ \tilde{x}_1(k) \end{bmatrix}$$

Then, in a compact way, the state-space Basic Model (BM) can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} x(k+1) &= Ax(k) + Bu(k) + Md(k) \\ y(k) &= Cx(k) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

2.2 Multiple Models

The IR technique can be applied to different datasets, resulting in distinct models: if the dataset spans an entire day, the identification process results in a DMP, while datasets limited to a single DP produce models specific to that DP. In this work, three DPs (breakfast, lunch, and dinner) are considered, resulting in the Basic Model Breakfast (BMB), Basic Model Lunch (BML), and Basic Model Dinner (BMD). The intervals for these DPs were defined as follows (see Toffanin et al. (2019)): $[t_B, t_L]$ for breakfast, $[t_L, t_D]$ for lunch, and $[t_D, t_B]$ for dinner. To maintain a conservative approach, the identification of the BMs is performed only for the DPs where the DMP performance was found to be unsatisfactory.

3. CONTROL STRATEGY DESIGN

To address intra-day variability in MPC design, two potential approaches can be considered: the first entails creating a periodic MPC that can manage the time-varying dynamics of the MMP, while the second, adopted in this work, involves implementing multiple switching MPCs. A Constrained MPC (C-MPC) was specifically designed for each model under consideration. This section details the development of a C-MPC for an individual model and explains the method used to combine multiple controllers to derive a unified control action.

3.1 Constrained MPC Design

Consider the linear discrete-time model (2). The optimal insulin therapy is defined by the C-MPC (Toffanin and Magni (2023a)) minimizing the following cost function:

$$\begin{aligned} J(x(k), u(\cdot), k) &= \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \left(\|y(k+i) - y_0(k+i)\|_q^2 + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \|u(k+i) - u_0(k+i)\|^2 \right) + \|x(k+N)\|_P^2 \end{aligned}$$

where $q > 0$ represents the output weight to be tuned, and N is the prediction horizon. Moreover, $\|x(k+N)\|_P = x(k+N)^\top P x(k+N)$, where P is a non-negative definite matrix computed by solving the following discrete-time Riccati equation:

$$P = A^\top P A + q C^\top C - A^\top P B (I + B^\top P B)^{-1} B^\top P A$$

Moreover, $y_0(k)$ and $u_0(k)$ are the output and the input normalized with respect to their equilibrium:

- (1) $y_0(k) = \tilde{y}(k) - G_b$ [mg/dl] is the difference between the reference value (\tilde{y}) of the sc glucose and the glucose basal value (G_b).

- (2) $u_0(k) = \tilde{u}(k) - i_b(k)$ [pmol/Kg] is the difference between the reference value (\tilde{u}) of the insulin profile and the insulin basal value (i_b).

The state $x(k)$ of the model, in general, is not measurable and thus it is estimated by a Kalman Filter (KF) (see Toffanin and Magni (2023a)) with sampling time T_s^{KF} . The KF leverages both the knowledge of the model and past information of insulin injections and meals to estimate the current state, thereby enhancing the accuracy of the optimization process. The Finite Horizon Optimal Control Problem (FHOCP) representing the C-MPC is defined as:

$$U^o(k) = \arg \min_{u(\cdot)} J(x(k), u(\cdot), k)$$

where $U^o(k) = [u^o(k) \dots u^o(k+N-2) u^o(k+N-1)]$ is the computed optimal control vector. Then, in view of the *Receding Horizon* principle, only the first element is applied.

3.2 Constraints

The FHOCP is subject to clinically-based constraints (Messori et al. (2014)) designed to prevent excessive insulin delivery, which could lead to hypoglycemia, and to avoid extended periods without insulin, which may cause elevated glucose levels, especially after a meal.

Pump Constraints The sc insulin pump has inherent physical limitations: injected insulin cannot be removed, necessitating a minimum insulin delivery constraint. Additionally, the pump has a hardware-dependent upper limit on insulin delivery. To enhance safety, stricter minimum constraints are applied to future insulin doses to reduce the risk of hypoglycemia, even in the presence of model uncertainties. The pump constraint is expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} u(k+i) \leq \min\{I(k) - \sum_{j=1}^{N_H} u(k+i-j), \bar{u}_{k+i}\} \\ u(k+i) \geq (\lambda(i) - 1) i_b(k+i) \end{cases}$$

with

$$\lambda(i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \forall i \in 0, N_\lambda, N_\lambda + 1, \dots, N \\ \bar{\lambda} & \forall i \in 1, \dots, N_\lambda - 1 \end{cases}$$

and with $i = 0, \dots, N-1$, $N_\lambda \leq N$, $\bar{u}_k = \bar{u} - i_b(k)$ where \bar{u} is the maximum insulin deliverable by the pump in a sample time k and $\bar{\lambda}$ is a tuning parameter. N represents the prediction horizon while N_H specifies the time interval in which the past insulin is considered.

$$I(k) = \nu \cdot \max \left(last_{ibolus}, \frac{y(k) - y_{th}}{CF} \right)$$

where $\nu > 0$ is a tuning parameter, $last_{ibolus}$ is the previous insulin meal bolus, y_{th} is a glucose threshold, and CF is the patient-specific Correction Factor.

Maximum Variation Constraint To ensure smoother control, the variation in insulin suggestions between time steps is limited as:

$$u(k) - u(k-1) \leq \zeta \cdot i_b(k)$$

where $\zeta > 0$ is a tuning parameter. This constraint is inactive during meal bolus delivery.

Fig. 2. Proposed closed-loop scheme for BG regulation. The gray part of the schema represents the *hybrid* part of the control loop: the meal announcement.

Ketone Bodies Constraint To prevent ketone body formation at high glucose levels ($y(k) \geq \bar{G}$), a minimum insulin delivery is ensured:

$$u(k) \geq \xi \cdot i_b(k) \quad \text{if } y(k) \geq \bar{G}$$

where \bar{G} is the safety glucose threshold, and $\xi > 0$ is a tuning parameter.

3.3 Combining Multiple C-MPCs

In this work, a dedicated C-MPC is implemented for each model (BMB, BML, BMD), resulting in MPC_B , MPC_L , and MPC_D .

Fig. 2 illustrates the control scheme, integrating meal announcements and insulin delivery. The variable \hat{m} denotes the estimated carbohydrate content of the meal m consumed by the patient. Upon meal announcement, the MPC controllers independently compute the optimal insulin variations relative to the basal insulin (i_b): u_B^o , u_L^o , and u_D^o . The optimal control inputs generated by these controllers are combined at each time step using a weighted averaging technique. The final optimal control input is expressed as:

$$u^o(k) = \alpha(k) \cdot u_B^o(k) + \beta(k) \cdot u_L^o(k) + \gamma(k) \cdot u_D^o(k), \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha(k)$, $\beta(k)$, $\gamma(k) \in [0,1]$ are weights that govern the contribution of each controller. The transition between controllers is managed through a switching mechanism. The method in Toffanin et al. (2019) originally implemented abrupt transitions (*hard switch*) within a predefined time frame. In this work a *soft switch* mechanism is introduced in order to take into account the physiological smooth changes in dynamics. All three MPCs are always active, but their contribution is weighted based on the specific interval. For instance, during periods far from t_B , t_L , and t_D , the dynamic described by a unique model dominates and the MPC based on that model will define the therapy. Close to t_B , t_L , and t_D , two models contribute concurrently to the dynamic description, with the signals α , β , and γ governing the smooth switching process: one weight remains constant at zero, while the other two use ramp signals to ensure a gradual shift (Fig. 3). The parameter t_{switch} defines half the total transition duration, enabling fine-tuning of the switching phase. The recommended insulin dose ($u^p = u^o + i_b$) is delivered by the pump, infusing insulin into the patient's sc tissue. The loop is completed with the measurement of Interstitial Glucose (IG) via the CGM device. Since meal announcement data must be externally provided, this system operates as a *hybrid* closed-loop configuration.

Fig. 3. Example of the transition between BMB and BML: the weight of BMB gradually decreases, while BML gains prominence. The contribution of BMD remains zero. The transition duration is $2 \cdot t_{switch}$.

3.4 C-MPC Calibration

The tunable parameter $q > 0$ plays a crucial role in the controller cost function: higher q values result in aggressive control with significant insulin adjustments, while lower q values yield conservative control with minimal insulin variation with respect to basal. The tuning of q was done through an iterative procedure on the in silico population in order to find the best value (q^o) for each virtual patient. The process begins synthesizing the C-MPC using a conservative initial q , testing it, and evaluating a performance index. Based on the results, q is adjusted, exploiting a run-to-run procedure (Toffanin et al. (2017)) until satisfactory performance is achieved or a stopping condition is met. In order to be conservative to the model uncertainties the value of q is reduced by a factor of 10 for the proposed switching algorithm.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

4.1 Metabolic Simulator

In this study, the UVA/Padova metabolic simulator (Visentin et al. (2018)) is used to evaluate the proposed MPC algorithms. Approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), this simulator serves as an in silico alternative to animal testing for insulin therapies, as it effectively replicates glucose patterns observed in human studies involving T1D patients. It features a virtual population of 300 subjects, including 100 adults, 100 adolescents, and 100 children, capturing the inter-patient variability characteristic of the real T1D population. The latest version of the simulator also accounts for intra-patient variability, simulating glucose fluctuations in Insulin Sensitivity (IS) throughout the day for a realistic depiction of metabolic behavior. It supports multi-day scenarios with intra-day IS variability and updated Carbohydrate Ratio (CR) distributions for breakfast, lunch, and dinner. For this work, the 37 adult subjects that showed problematic performance in Toffanin and Magni (2023b) were selected for analysis. The identification scenario (id-sc) lasts 53 hours during which the patient is treated with six meals as follows: 30 [g] for each breakfast, 60 [g] and 70 [g] for the first and second lunch, respectively, and 80 [g] and 90 [g] for the first and second dinner, respectively. The control operates in open-loop mode for two hours starting from

Fig. 4. Comparison between the real glucose (G , magenta) and the prediction of DMP (blue dashed line) and with BMB (green dotted line) for Patient A during breakfast DP. $FIT_{DMP} = 24.3\%$, $FIT_{BMB} = 59.8\%$.

midnight. The identification was then performed using the data generated with the id-sc and later evaluated on the testing scenario (test-sc). The test-sc lasts 30 hours and includes three meals as follows: a 60 [g] breakfast, a 50 [g] lunch and a 70 [g] dinner. This scenario is also used for evaluating the control performance of the proposed algorithms.

4.2 Performance Metrics

The performance of the identified model is evaluated using the index of fitting (FIT), defined as:

$$FIT = 100 \left(1 - \frac{\|\hat{Y}(k) - Y(k)\|}{\|Y(k) - \bar{Y}\|} \right)$$

where \bar{Y} is the mean of the CGM signal. FIT is equal to 100% if and only if $\hat{Y}(k) = Y(k) \forall k = 1, \dots, N$ (perfect prediction), and smaller than 100% otherwise. Note that FIT can also become negative. Control performance is further assessed using metrics such as Mean glucose (M), Standard Deviation (SD), percentage of time in the target range (70–180 [mg/dl], T_t), percentage in the tight target range (80–140 [mg/dl], T_{tt}), time in hyperglycemia (T_a) and hypoglycemia (T_b), and the number of Hypo-Treatments (HT) per patient ($\#\overline{ht}$). A hypoglycemia state is treated with a HT of 16 [g] of fast-acting glucose when $BG < 65$ [mg/dl]. A second HT is administered after 30 [min] if the hypoglycemic condition persists.

4.3 Identification Results

The FIT values obtained for the DMP and the models specific to each DP (BMB, BML, and BMD) reveal several performance differences. For the DMP, the FIT of the 37 patients (median (%) [25^{th} , 75^{th}] percentiles) was 20.9 [-18.3, 29.5] during breakfast, 16.1 [-43.7, 55.2] during lunch, and 31.8 [-21.6, 44.3] during dinner, indicating poor performance, particularly in the lunch and dinner periods. In contrast, the DP-specific models showed substantial improvements: BMB achieved a FIT of 29.3 [1.2, 55.6] during breakfast, BML 46.5 [27.5, 61.2] during lunch, and BMD 47.3 [27.2, 70.7] during dinner. Fig. 4 illustrates a comparison between the DMP and the BMB for a typical case study (Patient A) during breakfast in the test-sc. It is evident that the BMB offers more accurate predictions, successfully detecting the hypoglycemic peak following the

Fig. 5. Glucose trends achieved with MPC_{DM} and MPC_{MM} control strategies. OL is open-loop, CL is closed-loop, PP denotes the CL postprandial periods, and N is night. The red lines represent the tight target and the black lines represents the target range. Trends are shown in terms of glucose average (central solid lines), with [25^{th} , 75^{th}] percentiles as shading.

meal, which the DMP fails to capture. This discrepancy is likely due to significant variations in insulin sensitivity, and it is particular critical if this model is used for therapy definition.

4.4 Control Performance

The parameters used in the simulations are set to $T_s = 15$ [min] and $T_s^{KF} = 5$ [min], $N = N_\lambda = N_H = 60$ [min], $\lambda = 50$, $\xi = 0.3$, $\nu = 1$, $\zeta = 3$, $\bar{G} = 140$ [mg/dl], $G_b = 120$ [mg/dl] and $y_{th} = \tilde{y} = 115$ [mg/dl]. The calibration procedure starts with $q = 1$ and limits the number of iteration to 25. In this work, t_B is set to 5:00, t_L to 12:00, and t_D to 19:00. The switching process lasts for one hour ($t_{switch} = 30$ [min]).

Table 1 compares the performance metrics of the two algorithm used in this paper: the single MPC equipped with the DMP (MPC_{DM}) and the multiple switching MPC algorithm (MPC_{MM}) in the test-sc scenario. The results show that MPC_{MM} achieves lower average glucose levels compared to MPC_{DM} , especially during the night (N). Specifically, MPC_{MM} maintains an average glucose level of 114.68 [mg/dl], which is lower than the 120.48 [mg/dl] observed for MPC_{DM} . Additionally, MPC_{MM} demonstrates significantly reduced variability, with percentiles spanning approximately 7 [mg/dl], compared to 20 [mg/dl] for MPC_{DM} . MPC_{MM} demonstrates reduced glucose variability, as evidenced by lower standard deviations (SD). For instance, MPC_{MM} achieves 11.80 [6.38, 14.46] [mg/dl] at night compared to 14.44 [7.15, 34.81] [mg/dl] for MPC_{DM} . Regarding time in target (T_t), MPC_{MM} consistently outperforms MPC_{DM} , achieving 96.55% overall compared to MPC_{DM} 's 93.34%. In the tight target range (T_{tt}), MPC_{MM} shows a pronounced advantage, particularly during the night where it achieves 100.00% compared to 89.98% for MPC_{DM} . This advantage extends into the postprandial period, where MPC_{MM} attains 52.16% versus 44.79% for MPC_{DM} . Both strategies maintain minimal or no time below target (T_b), with MPC_{MM} achieving 0.00% even for the 75^{th} percentile, across all scenarios.

Table 1. Results obtained simulating the strategies MPC_{DM}, and MPC_{MM} on the test-sc scenario. The indices normally distributed are reported in terms of mean \pm SD and the others as median [25th, 75th] percentiles. ^a p-value < 0.001, ^b p-value < 0.01, ^c p-value < 0.05. Statistically significant results are highlighted in bold. O: Overall, N: Night, PP: PostPrandial.

		Validation scenario		
		O	N	PP
M [mg/dl]	MPC _{DM}	130.33 [117.87, 142.32]	120.48 [110.73, 130.25]	142.30 (\pm 27.07)
	MPC _{MM}	126.91^c [118.34, 137.17]	114.68^c [111.27, 118.18]	142.87 (\pm 21.64)
SD [mg/dl]	MPC _{DM}	25.80 [17.77, 34.29]	14.44 [7.15, 34.13]	23.63 [19.61, 32.19]
	MPC _{MM}	23.36 [18.64, 27.92]	11.80^c [8.38, 14.46]	25.00 [19.45, 29.43]
T_t (%)	MPC _{DM}	93.34 [73.94, 100.00]	100.00 [78.38, 100.00]	86.81 [69.17, 100.00]
	MPC _{MM}	96.55^b [90.39, 100.00]	100.00^a [100.00, 100.00]	91.94 [78.47, 100.00]
T_{tt} (%)	MPC _{DM}	63.18 [43.72, 81.37]	89.98 [53.26, 100.00]	44.79 (\pm 26.78)
	MPC _{MM}	79.12^a [61.59, 85.78]	100.00^a [97.16, 100.00]	52.16^b (\pm 26.79)
T_a (%)	MPC _{DM}	2.86 [0.00, 13.83]	0.00 [0.00, 2.30]	6.67 [0.00, 25.38]
	MPC _{MM}	3.45 [0.00, 8.60]	0.00^b [0.00, 0.00]	6.94 [0.00, 20.07]
T_b (%)	MPC _{DM}	0.00 [0.00, 4.43]	0.00 [0.00, 9.06]	0.00 [0.00, 0.00]
	MPC _{MM}	0.00^b [0.00, 0.00]	0.00^a [0.00, 0.00]	0.00 [0.00, 0.00]
$\# \overline{ht}$ per pat.	MPC _{DM}	0.00 [0.00, 2.25]	0.00 [0.00, 2.00]	0.00 [0.00, 0.00]
	MPC _{MM}	0.00^a [0.00, 0.00]	0.00^b [0.00, 0.00]	0.00 [0.00, 0.00]

MPC_{MM} exhibits slightly better performance in time above target (T_a), particularly during the night period, where its values are slower compared to MPC_{DM}. Finally, the number of hypoglycemic events per patient ($\# \overline{ht}$ per pat.) remains null for MPC_{MM} across all scenarios, underscoring its superior control over hypoglycemia when compared to MPC_{DM}. These observations are further supported by Fig. 5, which shows the global glucose profile of the closed-loop simulation on the test-sc scenario. During the nighttime, MPC_{MM} achieves more stable and lower glucose levels compared to MPC_{DM}, as indicated by the tighter orange curve and reduced variability. In the PP periods, glucose peaks are visible for both strategies, and while MPC_{MM} does not always exhibit lower peaks, it maintains narrower variability bands, reflecting improved consistency.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work highlights the benefits of a multiple model approach in accounting for patients' intra-day variability. The adoption of multiple DP-specific models resulted in a significant enhancement in predictive performance, with an average FIT index improvement of approximately 20% compared to the DMP. In terms of control performance, MPC_{MM} achieves superior glucose regulation compared to MPC_{DM}, particularly at night, with lower average glucose levels and reduced variability. While MPC_{MM} does not consistently produce lower glucose peaks during PP periods, it exhibits narrower variability bands and greater overall consistency. The enhanced time in target and tight target ranges, coupled with the complete absence of hypoglycemic events ($T_b = 0.00\%$, even at the 75th percentile), emphasizes MPC_{MM}'s ability to maintain stable and effective glucose control. Future work will focus on developing a unique periodic MPC integrated with the MMP for comparison with the current technique.

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